

Design and Implementation of a Low-Cost Portable EEG Based Brain Computer Interface

Enver Kaan Alptürk*, Yakup Kutlu

¹ Department of Computer Engineering, Iskenderun Technical University, Hatay, Turkey
E-mails: kaanalpturk@outlook.com, yakup.kutlu@iste.edu.tr

Abstract

Electroencephalography (EEG) are small amplitude and low frequency electrical signals received from the brain through electrodes placed in the skull. EEG signals can be easily disturbed due to external factors. For this reason, it must undergo a series of filtering processes at both the hardware layer and the software layer. EEG signals are already low amplitude signals. Since they also lose power during filtering, the signal output must be strengthened, that is, the amplitude must be increased. For this, generally Instrumentation amplifiers are using. In this study, an Instrumentation Amplifier circuit has been designed with electrodes that allow EEG recording, and the received signals are passed through a series of filtering processes in both the hardware layer and the software layer. It is aimed that the received brain signals can perform motor activities of disabled individuals by using the channels determined for "Motor Activities" in previous studies.

Keywords:

EEG, signal filtering, instrumentation amplifier, motor activity.

1. INTRODUCTION

EEG signals are biological electrical signals obtained from the brain. EEG signals are affected by the electrical and magnetic field in the environment and by all physical and mental activities of the individual to whom the electrode is attached (Alptürk & Kutlu, 2020, Mürşide et al., 2022a, Mürşide et al., 2022b). Therefore, before working on EEG signals, the received signals must be processed through a series of processes. These operations are basically filtering and amplitude amplification. Since EEG signals are of very low amplitude, they are difficult to detect. Because environmental factors, the tension resistance of the human

body, and the intensity of muscle signals make it difficult to detect brain signals. The most important environmental factor is the mains voltage. The frequency of this voltage, which is 60Hz in some regions, is 50Hz in some regions. The signals must be filtered so that the mains voltage does not affect the EEG signals. This filtering can be done at the hardware layer or at the software layer. The filter may need to be applied at the hardware layer in order to get instant results and minimize data processing time. EEG signals are examined in five main groups according to their frequency ranges (Table 1). Frequency ranges provide information

* Corresponding Author: Enver Kaan Alptürk, E-mail: kaanalpturk@outlook.com

about the psychological and biological states of the brain (Kumar & Bhuvaneswari, 2012).

Table 1: Grouping of EEG signals according to frequencies.

Group	Frequency	The cases where is seen
Delta	0.5-3.5 Hz	Adults: Occurs in sleep mode.
Tetha	4-7 Hz	Mostly occurs in stressful situations.
Alpha	8-12 Hz	When awake, it intensifies during the transition listening mode.
Beta	13-30 Hz	Seen in situations of concentration, stress, anxiety.
Gamma	30+ Hz	Seen in certain motor brain functions.

EEG signals are collected by some special electrodes and recorded by passing certain pre-processing with special circuits. Since the amplitudes of the EEG signals taken from the electrodes are below 100 μ V, it is very difficult to detect and distinguish them. In addition, the noise intensity is quite high. Therefore, the signals need to be filtered and their amplitudes amplified. Bo Luan et al. recorded EEG signals through skin screw electrodes in 2012. They used INA118 as first stage amplifier and TLC277CP as operational amplifier. They have been increased the signals obtained by means of a potentiometer between 5.76 and 101 times (Bo et al., 2012).

In 2013, L. Zhang et al. have been conducted a portable Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCI) study using two bipolar silver chloride electrodes. They have been filtered the 50 Hz mains voltage by applying a mode rejection filter, and then increased the signal 13.5 times. Finally, they have been filtered low-frequency noise with a 0.5 Hz passive RC High-Pass filter and increased the signal 51 times with the main amplifier. They have been used INA118 as amplifier (Zhang, Gao, et al., 2013).

Marzieh Moradi et al. have been used a CMOS-based amplifier on the portable EEG circuit they designed in 2021. The amplifier achieves a midband gain of 70 dB and a bandwidth of -3dB in the 0.1-212 Hz range. The

adjustable LPF has a cut-off frequency of 100 Hz. They have been used a continuous time second-order 100 Hz Gm-C Low-Pass Filter to reduce the ripples at the output of the amplifier. They have been achieved an output of 92 dB at the amplifier output (Moradi et al., 2021).

In this study, brain signals were obtained from the FP1 channel using 3 silver electrodes. The signals have been passed through the passive RC Low-Pass Filter and their amplitudes were amplified and transferred to the computer. The signals have been recorded during 3 different states and the accuracy of the study performed as a result of the frequency analysis of the signals is shown in the results section.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, disposable electrodes, which are also widely used in ECG systems, have been used to detect brain signals (Fig. 1). Disposable electrodes have been preferred because they already contain gel that can eliminate body resistance and are completely hygienic. Disposable electrodes contain a silver/silver chloride (Ag/AgCl) electrolyte and a gel attached to this electrolyte (Milli Eğitim Bakanlığı, 2011). Silver electrodes are the most suitable electrodes for capturing brain signals. It provides the advantage of low voltage resistance and high conductivity.

Figure 1. Disposable electrodes.

Electrodes placed at 3 points of the skull enabled data to be obtained from the FP1 channel in the frontal cortex. The voltage differences have been transferred to the circuit by connecting the electrode used for the main signal to the FP1 channel, the negative electrode to the FP2 channel and the electrode used for the grounding to the TP10 channel.

48.23 Hz passive RC Low-Pass filter have been used to minimize the noise generated in the signals. In this way, both meaningful signals for EEG can be distinguished and the effects of noise caused by 50 Hz city voltage are reduced. A 100 μF capacitor and a 33 Ohm resistor have been used for the RC Low-pass filter (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. RC Low-Pass filter

The output value of the signal filtered by the RC Low-Pass Filter is calculated using the formula in Equation 1 (RAO, 2006). The resistance (R) is calculated in ohms and the capacitor (C) in Farads.

$$F = \frac{1}{2\pi RC} \quad (1)$$

Since a 33 Ohm resistor and a 100 μF capacitor are used in this study, an output frequency of

$$F = \frac{1}{2\pi RC} = \frac{1}{2\pi \times 33 \times 0.0001} = 48.23 \text{ Hz} \quad (2)$$

is obtained as a result of applying the equation. The magnitude and phase values (Fig. 3) resulting from the 48.23 Hz RC Low-Pass Filter show how high frequency signals are attenuated.

Figure 3. Magnitude and phase values

With the simulation, sine waves of 20 Hz, 40 Hz, 60 Hz and 100 Hz were sent to the RC Low-Pass Filter, respectively, and it was observed that the filter reduced the amplitude of the high-frequency signals (Fig. 4).

Since the amplitudes of frequencies below 48.23 Hz also decrease a little after the filtering of the signals, it will be

difficult to distinguish the low amplitude EEG signals. For this reason, the AD620ARZ op-amp, which is an amplifier, have been connected to the circuit. The AD620 series provides the possibility to amplify the signal approximately 10000 times. AD620 gain is calculated with the formula in Equation 3 (Analog Devices, 2003).

Figure 4. RC Low-Pass filter simulation.

$$G = \frac{49.4K}{R_G} + 1 \quad (3)$$

Signal amplification in AD620 is done with the resistor R_G connected to the circuit. In this study, a 4.7 Ohm resistor was connected to the circuit and the gain was calculated as

$$G = \frac{49.4K}{R_G} + 1 = \frac{49.4K}{4.7} + 1 = 10.5K \quad (4)$$

In this direction, it is aimed to increase EEG signals smaller than 100 μ V to 0.5 - 1 V. The circuit diagram model is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Circuit diagram

The signal inputs of the designed circuit are connected to the electrodes placed in the Fp1 and Fp2 channels, and the reference input of AD620 is connected to the electrode placed in the Tp10 channel. With the created circuit model, the EEG signals received through the electrodes were transferred to the Arduino UNO via analogue pins. Data transferred from Arduino UNO to the computer via cable were processed on MATLAB. The 3D model of the top and interior view of the designed EEG recorder is shown

in Figure 6 and Figure 7, respectively. The device was placed on the skull by attaching disposable electrodes to the holes on Figure 7 and signal transmission was initiated. The model was printed with a 3D printer and the designed circuit and cables were arranged in such a way that they remained inside the model. The 3D headset model consists of 6 parts, 3 internal and 3 external. All parts are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 6. Top view of 3D headset model

Figure 7. Interior view of 3D headset model

Figure 8. All parts of 3D headset model

3. RESULTS

In this study, signals have been recorded based on three basic positions. The signals received from the Fp2 channel in the frontal cortex were transferred to the computer during nervous, resting state (eyes closed) and blinking

movements, and analyzed by Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) method. Since the signals lost their amplitude after filtering, it was observed that their amplitudes were in the range of 0.3V - 0.5V as a result of the amplification process. The results are shown in Figure 9, Figure 10 and Figure 11, respectively.

Figure 9. EEG signals received at the time of nervousness

Figure 10. EEG signals received during resting (Eyes Closed)

As a result of the examination of the recordings taken during 3 different states, the distinctive features of the signals obtained from the nervous state, resting state and blinking activities could be clearly observed. While it was observed in Figure 9 that the signal frequency increased considerably during the nervous state, both the amplitudes and frequencies of these signals decreased during the

resting state in Figure 10. In Figure 11, each eyes-blink created peaks of approximately 50 mV in the signal. In line with the results obtained, it was seen that different signals were obtained with their distinctive features after different brain thought states. Frequency analysis doing with FFT demonstrated the accuracy of the materials and methods used.

Figure 11. EEG signals received during eyes blinking

4. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In this study, a 3-electrode mobile EEG measurement system was designed. In line with the examination of the signals obtained with the design, it has been observed that the study has achieved its purpose and will contribute to future studies. EEG signals come to a very important point to understand the structure of the human brain and to popularize the use of brain-controlled devices. It is aimed to carry out specific studies with different electrode combinations that will be replaced in the future.

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